

Minimizing Memory in Parallel Task Graph Scheduling: Focusing on Average Consumption

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Abstract—The scheduling of applications represented as task graphs has been extensively studied in the literature, where the goal is often to minimize the total execution time. When accounting for the memory needs of tasks, many algorithms that strive to minimize the peak memory have been proposed, so that the execution can fit on a processor with limited memory. However, minimizing the peak memory may lead to a high memory consumption on average, which would deteriorate the performance when several such applications must be executed in parallel. In this case, one would hence rather minimize the average memory consumption over time for each application, since peak usage is likely not to happen at the same time for all applications. In this work, we formalize the problem of minimizing the average memory consumption of a task graph, with two different models, and we present optimal algorithms for some particular task graphs (k -chains, pumpkins). Building on these algorithms, we design heuristics for general graphs and we evaluate them through simulations. The results show that the heuristics often return solutions close to the optimal for a single task-graph application, and achieve in addition reasonably small peak memory usage. In a parallel setting, as we anticipated, minimizing the average memory of each application turns out to be more efficient than using a classical algorithm that focuses on minimizing the peak memory, hence demonstrating the usefulness of average memory consumption optimization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many high-performance applications are known for their extensive memory requirements. More recent computations run on High Performance Computing (HPC) platforms, such as the training of deep neural networks, making this issue particularly critical. Indeed, their massive memory consumption is often a sufficient motivation to include a large number of GPUs in the computation. The growing scale of these computations poses a challenge for the optimization of memory usage, which has motivated many research efforts aiming at reducing their memory footprint.

Among the approaches that have been explored, the scheduling of the operations is an important leverage to reduce the memory demand of computations. From the seminal work of Hong and Kung [1], several techniques have been derived, most of them trying to minimize the peak memory usage of a computation, that is, the maximum amount of memory required at any point during the computation [2], [3], [4]. The motivation behind this focus on the peak memory is to avoid costly input/output operations, by ensuring that a system is equipped with sufficient memory to handle the highest memory demand over time.

Fig. 1: Two ways of scheduling two applications (blue and green) in parallel and resulting total memory (red). Left: minimize peak memory of each application, which results in large total peak; Right: minimize average memory of each application, which results in lower total peak (even with larger individual peaks).

However, when multiple computations are processed concurrently on a shared memory system, it is rare that their memory peak coincides in time. Moreover, while reducing peak memory is essential, it can often lead to suboptimal average memory usage, which may lead to the parallel processing of several such computations using too much memory. In this context, minimizing the average memory usage over time becomes a more practical and efficient goal (see Fig. 1). The move to the average memory objective can also be motivated by an analogy with the caching problem, where recent studies suggest that optimizing the average cache usage for sequences of page accesses can significantly improve performance when multiple sequences are served in parallel [5].

The task graph paradigm has been proposed some time ago in the scheduling literature to model structured computations [6]. Vertices in the graph represent computation modules, or tasks, while edges represent the dependencies between these tasks in the form of input/output data. This representation has recently seen an increasing interest in HPC: to cope with the complexity and heterogeneity in modern computer design, many applications are now expressed as task graphs and rely on dynamic runtime schedulers for their execution, such as StarPU [7], StarSS [8], and PaRSEC [9]. We assume that the graph of tasks is known before the application and thus does not depend on the data itself.

In this paper, we tackle a two-fold problem. We study the challenge of minimizing the average memory usage for a single application modeled as a task graph. We then explore the effects of scheduling multiple task graphs in parallel on a shared-memory system, with the goal of optimizing the overall memory efficiency.

The main contributions of this paper are the following:

- We formally define the problem of optimizing the average memory of a task-graph for two different memory models, depending on whether the data produced by a task is the same for all its successors or not (Section II).
- We propose optimal algorithms for some specific classes of graphs (namely k -chains and pumpkin graphs, in Section IV).
- Based on the previous findings, we design heuristics to optimize the processing of general graphs (Section V).
- We present an experimental evaluation of the heuristics through simulations (Sections VI-A and Sections VI-B).
- We demonstrate through simulations that minimizing the average memory of each application is indeed a better way to optimize the total memory when processing the application in parallel (Section VI-C).

Related work is discussed in Section III. We conclude and discuss future work directions in Section VII.

II. MODEL

We focus on task graphs represented by a directed acyclic graph (DAG), G . We denote by $V = \{a_1, \dots, a_n\}$ the set of vertices of G , where each vertex represents a task. Each task $a_i \in V$ takes a fixed time t_i to be executed. E is the set of edges of G , which represent data dependencies between tasks. We denote by $V^+(a_i)$ the set of successors of a_i in G . If $a_j \in V^+(a_i)$, then a_i produces some output data that is required by a_j as input data. This means that we need to execute task a_i before task a_j .

Memory models. We consider two distinct models for representing the output data: the *single data* model and the *multiple data* model.

In the *single data* model, each task a_i produces only one piece of data as output, with a size of w_i . This data is stored in memory as soon as task a_i begins its execution and remains there until all of its successor tasks have started. Once every successor task $a_j \in V^+(a_i)$, has begun execution, the data produced by a_i can be safely removed from memory. An example of this model is illustrated in Figure 2.

In contrast, the *multiple data* model involves task a_i generating distinct output data for each of its successors. Each piece of data is removed from memory as soon as its corresponding successor starts execution. In this model, each output data can have a unique size, so we denote the weight of the edge $(a_i, a_j) \in E$ as $w_{i,j}$, representing the size of the data generated by task a_i for task a_j . An example of this model is shown in Figure 3.

In both models, we represent the associated weighted DAG as (G, t, w) . While the distinction in edge weights may seem subtle, it leads to different optimization challenges and algorithmic solutions. We now detail the associated optimization problems.

Optimization problems. For both memory models, the problem is to find a schedule that minimizes the average memory consumption of the processor, given a task graph G . All tasks have to be ordered for a sequential execution

Fig. 2: Pumpkin graph in the *single data* model.

Fig. 3: 3-chain graph in the *multiple data* model.

order, while respecting the constraints imposed by the graph structure. Hence, the execution always take a total time of $\sum_{i=1}^{|V|} t_i$. We formally define a schedule:

Definition 1 (Schedule). *Let (G, t, w) be a weighted DAG. A schedule is represented by a function ϕ that associates to each task its starting time ($\phi : V \rightarrow \{1, \dots, \sum_{i=1}^{|V|} t_i\}$). It is a valid schedule if and only if:*

- $\forall a_i, a_j \in V, \phi(a_j) \geq \phi(a_i) + t_i$ or $\phi(a_i) \geq \phi(a_j) + t_j$ (no task overlap)
- $\forall a_i \in V, \phi(a_i) + t_i \leq \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j$ (no idle time)
- $\forall (a_i, a_j) \in E, \phi(a_i) < \phi(a_j)$ (data dependencies)

Since we enforce that all tasks are finished at time $\sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j$, the schedule is totally defined by an ordering of the tasks L_ϕ , also called an arrangement.

For instance, $L_\phi = (1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8)$ corresponds to a valid schedule ϕ for the graph in Figure 2 with eight tasks.

Given a schedule ϕ , in the *single data* model, the data of weight w_i stays in memory for a duration $\max_{a_j \in V^+(a_i)} \phi(a_j) - \phi(a_i)$, i.e., from the start of task a_i until the last successor a_j has started its execution. In order to minimize the average memory usage, we aim at minimizing the weighted sum of the time each data stays in memory. This cost function is actually a known function on graphs [10], that is called the weighted sum cut:

Definition 2 (Weighted Sum Cut (WSC)). *Given a valid schedule ϕ for a DAG G , the weighted sumcut of ϕ is:*

$$WSC_G(\phi) = \sum_{a_i \in V} w_i \max_{a_j \in V^+(a_i)} (\phi(a_j) - \phi(a_i)).$$

For the *multiple data* memory model, the data between a_i and a_j stays in memory for a duration of $\phi(a_j) - \phi(a_i)$. This leads to a cost function that is also a known function on graphs, called the weighted linear arrangement. It has been already been studied a lot in the literature, see for instance [11] or [12]:

Definition 3 (Weighted Linear Arrangement (WLA)). *Given a valid schedule ϕ for a DAG G , the weighted linear arrange-*

ment cost of ϕ is:

$$WLAG(\phi) = \sum_{(a_i, a_j) \in E} w_{i,j} (\phi(a_j) - \phi(a_i)).$$

For the definition of both cost functions, we consider that the output data of task a_i is produced as soon as the task starts. This is only for simplicity and does not impact the algorithms: if it was produced at the end, it would only change the cost of a schedule by a constant.

Both of these objective functions are directly related to the average memory consumption of a schedule, as we can obtain the average memory used by dividing WSC or WLA by the makespan of the schedule, which is a constant. Hence, we focus on the study of minimizing WSC and WLA .

Finally, we give a simple definition of the peak memory, that is detailed in [3]:

Definition 4 (Peak memory). *For both memory models, the peak memory consumption of a schedule ϕ is the highest amount of memory consumed throughout the execution of ϕ . More formally, for a graph (G, t, w) , we define:*

$$PEAK_{Mult. Data}(\phi) = \max_{1 \leq t \leq \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j} \sum_{\phi(a_i) \leq t < \phi(a_j)} w_{i,j}.$$

$$PEAK_{Sing. Data}(\phi) = \max_{1 \leq t \leq \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j} \sum_{\substack{\exists a_j \in V^+(a_i) \\ \phi(a_i) \leq t < \phi(a_j)}} w_i.$$

Graph types. Minimizing the average or the peak memory on general directed graphs is NP-complete on both models (see Section III), hence we consider some special classes of graphs to assess the problem complexity.

Definition 5 (In-tree, out-tree, k -chain). *An in-tree (resp. out-tree) is a directed graph where all the vertices have at most one outgoing (resp. incoming) edge. An out-tree T is a k -chain if its root has out-degree k and it is the only node with multiple successors (see Figure 3 for an example).*

Definition 6 (Pumpkin). *A graph G is a pumpkin graph if it has one source of out-degree k and in-degree 0, one target of in-degree k and out-degree 0, and all other nodes have in-degree and out-degree 1 (see Figure 2 for an example).*

Definition 7 (Series Parallel (SP)). *G is a SP graph if:*

- G is just a source and a target $s \rightarrow t$; or
- G is the series composition of two SP graphs (merging the target of the first to the source of the second); or
- G is the parallel composition of K SP graphs (all the sources are linked to a new node s and all the targets are linked to a new node t).

III. RELATED WORK

While most of the literature on task graph scheduling focuses on makespan minimization, there have been several studies on graph traversals for minimizing the peak memory, in particular in the domain of numerical linear

algebra. The first studies concentrated on tree-shaped task graphs. Liu [13] described how the storage requirements and computational dependencies of matrix factorization can be represented by in-trees, and has later shown how to find a peak memory-minimizing traversal of the tree [14], [2]. The problem of scheduling a task graph under memory constraints also appears in the processing of scientific workflows whose tasks require large I/O files. Such workflows arise in many scientific fields, such as image processing, genomics, and geophysical simulations. The problem of task graphs handling large data has been identified by Ramakrishnan et al. [15], who propose some simple heuristics. In the context of quantum chemistry computations, Lam et al. [16] also considered task trees. More recently, progress has been made towards more general graphs: Kayaaslan et al. [3] have proposed an optimal algorithm for SP-graphs under the *multiple data* model, while the problem has been shown NP-complete under the *single data* model by Jin et al. [4], who also propose a polynomial-time algorithm for SP-graphs with bounded degree. Minimizing the peak memory for general directed graphs is NP-complete even in the *single memory* model, as it generalizes the pebble game introduced by Sethi and Ullman [17], [18].

The WSC and WLA problems, related to minimizing the average memory under the *single data* and *multiple data* problems, have both been shown NP-complete on general directed graphs [19], [20]. Sum-cut problems have been studied on directed graphs only in the unweighted case; Bossart et al. [20] have proposed an algorithm for out-trees in $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. A polynomial-time algorithm for a specific subclass of SP graphs (reduced 2-terminal series parallel graphs) has also been designed by Achouri et al. [21].

For (unweighted) Linear Arrangement problems, linear algorithms have been proposed for out-trees and pumpkins [22]. One of the closest results to the present study is the algorithm from Adolphson & Hu [11], which presents a solution for the WLA problem on out-trees, with complexity $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. Our Lemmas 1 and 2 below show that this algorithm can be also used on in-trees for WLA and WSC . In Section IV-C, we make use of this algorithm and extend some of the results from [11] to out-trees for the WSC problem.

Figure I summarizes the existing results for Sum Cut and Linear Arrangement problems, and introduces the main results of the present paper. Note that both peak memory minimization and average memory minimization are variants of linear arrangement and sum cut problems on graphs, which have been extensively studied in the undirected case [23].

Problem Type	Weighted	Unweighted
Linear Arrgt. (multiple data memory model)	General : NP-C [19]	General : NP-C [19]
	Out-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ [11]	Out-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n)$ [22]
	In-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ Lemma 1	In-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n)$ Lemma 1
	Pumpkin : $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ Theorem 1	Pumpkin : $\mathcal{O}(n)$ [22]
Sum Cut (single data memory model)	General : NP-C [20]	General: NP-C [20]
	In-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ Lemma 2+[11]	r-2TSPG : $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ [21]
	k -chain : $\mathcal{O}(n^{k+1} \log(n))$ Theorem 2	In-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n)$ Lemma 2
	Pumpkin : $\mathcal{O}(n^{k+1} \log(n))$ Theorem 3	Out-tree : $\mathcal{O}(n)$ [20]

TABLE I: Main results for the two memory models.

IV. OPTIMAL ALGORITHMS

Since the problems are NP-complete for general graphs, we focus on special classes of graphs in order to derive exact algorithms. We start with some preliminaries in Section IV-A. Then, we first present an optimal algorithm for *WLA* on pumpkins in Section IV-B, before discussing the more complicated *WSC* problem in Section IV-C.

A. Preliminaries

Before designing algorithms for our optimization problems, we present a few reductions between different problems on trees. These equivalences will be used as subroutines later on, allowing us to transform out-trees into in-trees. Because they rely on very simple graph transformations, these reductions do not add any algorithmic complexity to our problem. Hence, Lemma 1 shows the equivalence between in-trees and out-trees for the *WLA* problem, while Lemma 2 shows the equivalence of *WLA* and *WSC* on in-trees.

Definition 8 (Reverse graph and schedule). Let $G = (V, E)$ be a directed graph. We define its reverse graph $G' = (V, E')$ such that $(a_i, a_j) \in E' \Leftrightarrow (a_j, a_i) \in E$.

Given ϕ a schedule for G such that $L_\phi = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$, we define its reverse schedule ϕ' such that $L_{\phi'} = (a_n, \dots, a_1)$.

Lemma 1. Let G be a weighted out-tree and ϕ be a schedule for G . Let G' be the reverse graph of G and ϕ' be the reversed schedule of ϕ . Then ϕ' is an optimal schedule for *WLA* on G' if and only if ϕ is an optimal schedule for *WLA* on G .

Proof sketch. One can first easily verify that ϕ' is a schedule for G' . We then prove that the cost of ϕ for G and ϕ' for G' only differ by a constant, and derive the optimality of ϕ' . The full version of this proof can be found in Appendix A3. \square

Lemma 2. Let T be an in-tree and ϕ a valid schedule for T . $WSC_T(\phi) = WLA_T(\phi)$.

Proof. For in-trees, each node has exactly one successor, hence the equality:

$$\begin{aligned} WSC_T(\phi) &= \sum_{u \in V} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\ &= \sum_{(u,v) \in E} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) = WLA_T(\phi). \end{aligned}$$

\square

B. Weighted Linear Arrangement on pumpkins

In this section, we focus on the *multiple data* memory model, and we design an $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ algorithm to solve *WLA* on pumpkins. The idea of splitting the graph at its min-cut originates from [3], but the proofs are very different considering that we do not have the same objective function. We first note that we can easily find a min-cut in the pumpkin, by decreasing the weights on each chain of the pumpkin, thanks to Lemma 3.

Lemma 3. Let G be a pumpkin graph of sink t , with $c = (a_1, \dots, a_i)$ a chain of G with non-zero weights. If G' is the

Fig. 4: Min-cut (S, T) of a graph G .

(a) Lexicographic schedule ϕ

(b) New schedule $\psi = \phi[S] + \phi[T]$

Fig. 5: Schedule transformation with a cut.

graph where all the weights along c are decreased by 1, then an optimal schedule for *WLA* on G' is optimal for *WLA* on G .

Proof sketch. Because of the structure of the graph, data from the chain c is stored in memory up until the last node is executed. Whatever the schedule considered, this data stays the same amount of time in memory, therefore adding one to the whole chain only changes the cost by a constant. The detailed proof can be found in Appendix A7. \square

Given a pumpkin graph G , this lemma tells us that we can transform G into an equivalent pumpkin graph where each chain has at least one edge of weight 0. In particular, we can transform G into a pumpkin G' of min-cut 0, and such that if ϕ is optimal for *WLA* on G' , it is optimal for *WLA* on G .

The idea is then to schedule first all the tasks before the cut, and then the remaining task, hence dealing with two trees on each side of the cut (see for instance Figure 4). This key result is formalized in Lemma 4:

Lemma 4. Given a pumpkin graph G with a directed cut (S, T) of weight 0, there is an optimal schedule ϕ for *WLA* on G such that $\forall u \in S, v \in T, \phi(u) < \phi(v)$.

Proof sketch. The schedule is divided into two parts, hence we formally define a sub-schedule on a subset of tasks S :

Definition 9. Let $G = (V, E)$ be a DAG, and $S \subseteq V$ a subset of the vertices. Given a schedule ϕ of G with $L_\phi = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$, we define $\phi_{[S]}$ such that $L_{\phi_{[S]}} = (a'_1, \dots, a'_j)$ with $\{a'_1, \dots, a'_j\} = S$, as the schedule following the same task order as in ϕ on the subset of tasks S .

Let ϕ be an optimal schedule for *WLA* on G . We define $\psi = \phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}$, as shown in Figure 5, where all tasks of S are scheduled before tasks of T . We prove that ψ is a valid and optimal schedule for *WLA* on G . The optimality is proven by comparison with ϕ : for any edge of the pumpkin, we prove that the transformation from ϕ to ψ strictly decreases

the edge cost. The full case disjunction can be found in Appendix A8. \square

Lemma 4 tells us that we will always be able to find an optimal schedule for WLA on a pumpkin that stops at the min-cut. In particular, it means that we can solve both sides of the min-cut independently. This allows us to reuse algorithms that were developed for out-trees and in-trees, and obtain a schedule for pumpkins.

Theorem 1. *Given a pumpkin graph G and a min-cut (S, T) , let ϕ_S be an optimal schedule for WLA on the out-tree S , and ϕ_T be an optimal schedule for WLA on the in-tree T . Then, $\phi = \phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}$ is an optimal schedule for WLA on G , and it can be found in time $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$.*

Proof sketch. This theorem is a direct implication from Lemmas 3 and 4. Since finding a min-cut in a pumpkin can be done in linear time, and that solving WLA on trees takes time $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$, the schedule can be constructed in time $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. \square

C. Weighted Sum Cut on k -chain trees and pumpkins

The problem turns out to be much more complicated for WSC and the *single data* model, because we cannot easily decrease weights on each chain. Indeed, the initial data is shared by all chains of the pumpkin. Actually, the problem is even difficult on k -chains. Hence, we start the study on k -chains, before extending the algorithm for pumpkins.

WSC on k -chains. The main source of inspiration for this section is the paper published in 1973 by Adolphson & Hu [11], which considers the linear arrangement problem on out-trees. Although our proof is slightly different because of the different graph and objective function, there are some similarities, since we reuse some definitions. We follow the same proof principle, but some additional difficulties emerge from the WSC problem. After proving some useful results on the shape of an optimal schedule for WSC, we exhibit the real difficulty of the problem, and we give an $\mathcal{O}(n^{k+1})$ exact algorithm.

Step 1 – Obtaining a compressed graph. We define below a quantity on vertices that directly correlates to the schedule order of nodes. In [11], this was sufficient to find an optimal schedule. Here, we need some additional work because of the very first edge of the chain that has a shared dependency with all the chains.

Definition 10 (Ratio). *Let G be a k -chain tree and a_i, a_j, a_k elements of V such that $(a_i, a_j) \in E$ and $(a_j, a_k) \in E$. We define the ratio of a_j by:*

$$R_G(a_j) = \frac{w_{a_i, a_j} - w_{a_j, a_k}}{t_j}.$$

Whenever it is possible, we drop the indice G from this ratio.

Definition 11 (Compressed graph). *A k -chain graph G is a compressed graph if and only if:*

- *The weight of the edges is decreasing along each chain.*

Fig. 6: Two phases of a schedule on a 3-chain.

- *The ratio of each node is decreasing along each chain.*

Lemma 5. *Let G be a k -chain tree. There exists a compressed k -chain tree G' such that an optimal schedule for WSC on G is also an optimal schedule for WSC on G' .*

Proof sketch. This proof is fairly long and involves the definition of new properties on edges. It closely follows what has been done in [11], see Appendix A for details. \square

Because this proof is constructive, the main take-away from Lemma 5 is that we can construct a compressed graph G' that is equivalent to G , in that solving the WSC problem on G' gives the optimal schedule for G . From now on, we always work on the compressed representation of G .

Step 2 – Splitting the schedule. After having studied the local structure of the chains to get a compressed representation of G , we now delve into the global structure of a schedule.

Let us consider a k -chain G of root s . It turns out that the relative order of the schedule of nodes entirely depends on whether it is done before or after all the successors of s have been scheduled. For this, we split a schedule ϕ into two phases.

Definition 12 (Phases of a schedule). *Let s be the root of the k -chain. We say that a_i is in the first phase of the schedule ϕ if $\phi(a_i) \leq \max_{a_j \in V^+(s)} \phi(a_j)$. Otherwise, we say that u is in the second phase of the schedule. An example of a split schedule is given in Figure 6.*

The intuition behind these two phases is the following: in the first phase, we have a data that is shared among all chains, and we cannot use the traditional WLA algorithm. However, in the second phase, we have no more data in common, and we can reuse the same results as in the *multiple data* case.

Now that these two phases are properly defined, we show that they both have unique properties, that make scheduling nodes inside each phase a simple process. For the first phase, we can associate to each chain a new quantity that directly defines how it should be ordered. For the second phase, the nodes can be scheduled by order of decreasing ratio, like what was done in the WLA case [11]. Both orderings are very easy to compute. This emphasizes that the real difficulty of the problem lies in finding one single cut: the one that cuts the schedule in its first and second phases. This also paves the way to an $\mathcal{O}(n^k)$ algorithm to solve the WSC problem on k -chain trees.

Fig. 7: Crossing in the first phase.

The next two lemmas handle the schedule of the chains in the first phase of the schedule. We show that the chains do not cross each other. As soon as we start scheduling a chain in the first phase, we schedule the rest of the nodes of this chain immediately after. We then show that starting each chain by order of decreasing relative "weight" gives an optimal ordering.

Lemma 6. *Let T be a k -chain tree and ϕ an optimal schedule for T . In the first phase of ϕ , once a chain starts being scheduled, it will continue until the first phase ends.*

Proof. We only focus on two chains that cross in the first phase of the schedule of ϕ . It is as if the chains start with a weight of 0 as their associated data is kept in memory during the whole phase 1. We let a'_1, \dots, a'_j be the part of the chains that crossed another one, between a_i and a_{i+1} , as depicted in Figure 7.

We consider the schedule ϕ' , whose only difference with ϕ is that a_{i+1} is scheduled before the elements a'_1, \dots, a'_j . It is a valid schedule as the two chains are independent. Thus, we have $WSC(\phi) \leq WSC(\phi')$. This gives an immediate contradiction:

$$\begin{aligned} WSC(\phi) &\leq WSC(\phi') \\ \sum_{l=1}^j t'_l w_{i,i+1} + t_{i+1} w'_{j,j+1} &\leq \sum_{l=1}^j t'_l w_{i+1,i+2} \\ w_{i,i+1} &< w_{i+1,i+2} \end{aligned}$$

This is a direct contradiction with the definition of a compressed graph, that says that the weight of the edges should be decreasing along the chains. Therefore, an optimal schedule cannot have such a crossing in the first phase of a schedule. \square

Lemma 7. *Suppose we know that the chains $c_1 = (a_{1,1}, \dots, a_{1,k_1}), \dots, c_{k-1} = (a_{k-1,1}, \dots, a_{k-1,k_{k-1}})$ belong to the first phase of the schedule. If w_i is the weight of the outgoing edge from chain c_i , then ordering the chains by decreasing value of $t_i / \sum_{j=1}^{k_i} w_{i,j}$ gives an optimal solution to WSC.*

Proof sketch. We know from Lemma 6 that the first phase of the schedule only has chains scheduled continuously. We

Fig. 8: Exchanging two nodes in the 2nd phase of a schedule.

prove by contradiction that any schedule that is not ordered by decreasing value of $t_i / \sum_{j=1}^{k_i} w_{i,j}$ is sub-optimal. The full proof can be found in Appendix A5. \square

Lemma 8. *Let T be a k -chain tree and ϕ an optimal ordering for WSC. If a_1, \dots, a_n are the nodes of the second phase of ϕ , then they are scheduled in order of non-increasing ratio. We have, for all $i < k$, $R(a_i) \geq R(a_{i+1})$.*

Proof. Let G be a k -chain graph. Suppose there exists an optimal schedule ϕ that has some increasing ratios in the second phase of the schedule. Let us say that we have $R(a_i) < R(a_j)$ and $\phi(a_i) + 1 = \phi(a_j)$.

Let ϕ' be the copy of ϕ except that a_i and a_j are switched. ϕ and ϕ' are represented in Figure 8. It is a valid schedule as a_i and a_j are from two different chains (we work on a compressed graph, so ratios are already decreasing along a chain). From the optimality of ϕ , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} WSC(\phi) &\leq WSC(\phi') \\ w_{i,i+1} t_j + w_{j-1,j} t_i &\leq w_{i-1,i} t_j + w_{j,j+1} t_i \\ \frac{w_{j-1,j} - w_{j,j+1}}{t_j} &\leq \frac{w_{i-1,i} - w_{i,i+1}}{t_i} \\ R(a_j) &\leq R(a_i) \end{aligned}$$

This contradicts the hypothesis that the ratios were increasing. \square

Theorem 2. *Let G be a k -chain graph with chains of size n_1, \dots, n_k .*

Given a directed cut C , if there exists an optimal ordering ϕ for WSC on G such that C is exactly the first and second phase of ϕ , then we can find an optimal ordering for WSC in $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$.

Hence, there is an $\mathcal{O}\left(\prod_{i=1}^k n_i n \log(n)\right)$ algorithm to find an optimal solution to the WSC problem, by enumerating all possible cuts.

Proof. The proof here mainly relies on the previous two lemmas: Lemma 7 and Lemma 8. The first one states that given the nodes in the beginning of the schedule, one can find an optimal arrangement of the chains by sorting them by decreasing value of $t_i / \sum_{j=1}^{k_i} w_{i,j}$. The second says that sorting the end of the schedule by decreasing ratio gives an optimal solution. Both steps can be done in $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ times. Because we know that there is an optimal ϕ that has such a set of beginning and end, and that both sides are solved optimally, this gives us an optimal solution for the whole graph.

Because all the cuts are enumerated, we are sure to find at least one optimal schedule, thus the algorithm is correct. There are exactly $\prod_{i=1}^k n_i$ cuts possible in G , as we can cut the chain i at n_i different places (we considered that not taking the first node of the chain is not possible in the beginning of the schedule). Then, the algorithm to find the corresponding schedule runs in $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$, hence the final complexity. \square

WSC on pumpkins. We are now ready to deal with pumpkins, building upon the optimal algorithm for WSC on k -chains. Since the algorithm is exponential for k -chains (see Theorem 2), we also derive an exponential algorithm for pumpkins. We even prove that we cannot find an exact algorithm with better complexity for pumpkins than for k -chain trees, using a polynomial reduction.

We extend the definition of first and second phase from k -chains to pumpkin graphs. The first phase is still constituted of the nodes scheduled before the first data is removed from memory. It turns out that the lemmas for the first part of the schedule still work for pumpkins. In particular, Lemma 7 states that given the cut (S, T) of the first and second phase of an optimal schedule, one can find an optimal schedule for the first phase in $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$.

Let $G = (V, E)$ be a pumpkin graph, of chains c_1, \dots, c_k . Let (S, T) be a cut of G . We define the graph $G' = (T \cup \{s\}, E')$ such that (see Fig. 9):

- $\forall (u, v) \in E, u \in T \Leftrightarrow (u, v) \in E'$;
- $\forall (u, v) \in E, u \in S \wedge v \in T \Leftrightarrow (s, v) \in E'$.

Fig. 9: The graph G' .

Lemma 9. Let ϕ' be an optimal schedule for WLA on G' (removing s). If there exists an optimal schedule ϕ for WSC on G such of first phase S and second phase T , then $\phi_{[S]} + \phi'$ is also an optimal schedule for WSC on G .

The proof of this lemma is mainly computational, it is detailed in Appendix A6.

Theorem 3. Let G be a pumpkin graph with k chains of size n_1, \dots, n_k . We can find an optimal schedule for WSC on G in $\mathcal{O}\left(\prod_{i=1}^k n_i n \log(n)\right)$.

Proof. It follows the same idea as for Theorem 2. Given an optimal schedule ϕ for WSC on G , we consider the cut (S, T) such that $\phi_{[S]}$ is the first phase of ϕ . From Lemma 7, we know that from (S, T) , we can find an optimal first phase of an optimal schedule for WSC on G . We can also compute an optimal schedule for WLA on G' by using the algorithm described in Theorem 1, which has complexity $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. Then, using Lemma 4, we know that we can merge the two obtained schedule to get an optimal schedule for WSC on G .

It then remains to find such a cut (S, T) . This can be done in a bruteforce way: each branch c_i can be cut at n_i different places, so there are $\prod_{i=1}^k n_i$ different cuts. Hence, the final complexity of the algorithm is $\mathcal{O}\left(\prod_{i=1}^k n_i n \log(n)\right)$. \square

V. HEURISTICS AND LOWER BOUNDS

Building upon the previous results, we design heuristics to find efficient schedules for general DAGs for the WLA and WSC problems. The first set of heuristics are simple greedy heuristics that are used as baselines. We then present a more involved heuristic that builds upon the optimal algorithms for pumpkins from Section IV. We also present heuristics for k -chains on WSC, used in the heuristic on general DAGs while the optimal algorithm has high complexity. Finally, we introduce lower bounds for the WSC problem on k -chains in Section V-D, with the aim of studying the performance of the heuristics in Section VI.

A. Greedy algorithms for general DAGs

The greedy algorithms create a schedule starting from the source node of the graph, iteratively choosing among the available nodes the one that minimizes a given cost function. We design three variants of the greedy algorithm, using these cost functions:

- GREEDY-MEM: Choose the vertex that frees as much memory as possible;
- GREEDY-TIME: Choose the vertex that takes the shortest time to execute;
- GREEDY-RATIO: Choose the vertex with the biggest ratio.

The pseudocode of the greedy algorithms can be found in Appendix B1. These algorithms apply to any graph and constitute a comparison baseline for the more specialized algorithms. Because each iteration requires an insertion into a priority queue, their time complexity is $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$.

B. An involved heuristic for general DAGs

To compute a schedule for a general DAG, we proceed in two phases: we first convert the graph to an SP-graph (SPization), and then we recursively find a schedule for the SP-graph. In the first phase, we use the key idea from [24]: first force the graph to have only one source and target, and then add some nodes of duration 0 and edges of weight 0 to transform the structure of the graph into the structure of a parallel graph. This process is fairly complex, hence we do not describe it entirely here, but a C implementation of this algorithm is available in [25]. Since we are adding nodes and synchronization points, we have no guarantee that the schedule found in the transformed graph corresponds to an optimal schedule in the original graph. However, since we modify the graph as little as possible, we hope that we can still achieve a low average memory for the original graph.

The second part of the process consists in recursively building a schedule. Given an SP graph G :

- If $G = s \rightarrow t$, we simply return the schedule (s, t) ;
- If $G = G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ is a series composition of SP graphs, then let ϕ_i be the schedule returned by the algorithm on G_i for $i = \{1, 2\}$, and we return $\phi_1 + \phi_2$;

- If G is the parallel composition of G_1, \dots, G_k , then let ϕ_i be the schedule returned by the algorithm on G_i for $1 \leq i \leq k$. We create the pumpkin graph G' , with k branches, where the branch c_i is the graph G_i linearized according to the schedule ϕ_i . The edge weights remain those of G_i . We run the exact algorithm on the pumpkin G' , and return this schedule.

This two-phase process uses the optimality of the pumpkin algorithms to produce a good schedule on a transformed graph. Since the pumpkin algorithm is of polynomial complexity for *WLA* (see Theorem 1), we obtain a polynomial-time algorithm, denoted *AVGSPALGO*.

However, the problem is more complex for *WSC*, and it builds on an exponential algorithm for k -chains (see Theorem 2, complexity in $\mathcal{O}(n^{k+1} \log(n))$). Hence, we present below polynomial-time heuristics for *WSC* on k -chains, that will be more usable in practice.

C. Heuristics for *WSC* on k -chains

A first option is to use the greedy algorithms presented above in Section V-A. However, these algorithms have a limited view of the graph and may perform poorly, which is why we also propose some algorithms based on cuts. Recall from Section IV-C that once we know which cut is used in the graph, finding an optimal schedule can be done in $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$. We use this observation to construct a new class of algorithms that focus on finding a *good* cut. The first approach is simply to draw random cuts, generate the corresponding schedule, and take the one that minimizes the sum cut cost. The pseudocode for this *RANDOM-CUT* algorithm can be found in Appendix B2.

The problem remains that, in order for our algorithm to be efficient, we have to draw a polynomial amount of cuts, among a set of exponential size. It turns out that in practice, this is pretty inefficient. Hence, we refine this heuristic through some guided exploration with a local search.

The idea of *LOCAL-SEARCH* is the following (see Algorithm 1): starting from a random cut of the graph, we try to do some small modifications and see if it improves the solution. If it does, then we take this new solution and continue the exploration, otherwise we discard it and start again from the previous solution. In our case, the modification consists in adding or removing one node on one of the chains (see function *ModifyCut*).

D. Lower bounds for the *WSC* problem on k -chains

Because of the high complexity of the optimal algorithm for *WSC*, we cannot use it for large instances, and hence evaluate the performance of the heuristics. Therefore, we design lower bounds that will allow us to assess how close the heuristics might be to the optimal. The first lower bound is a reduction to the linear arrangement problem, since *WLA* can be solved optimally in polynomial time, while the second one uses linear programming.

Algorithm 1: *minSCLocalSearch*(G, N)

```

1 Function LocalSearch( $G$ ):
2   bestCut  $\leftarrow$  RandomCut();
3   bestSched  $\leftarrow$  ConstructSchedule( $G$ , bestCut);
4   for  $i = 1$  to  $N$  do
5     newCut  $\leftarrow$  ModifyCut(bestCut);
6     newSched  $\leftarrow$  ConstructSchedule( $G$ , newCut);
7     if  $Cost(newSched, G) < Cost(bestSched, G)$  then
8       bestSched  $\leftarrow$  newSched;
9       bestCut  $\leftarrow$  newCut;
10  return bestSched;
11 Function ModifyCut( $cut$ ):
12   $(c_1, \dots, c_l) \leftarrow$  RandomBranch( $G$ );
13  if RandomBool() then  $cut.add(c_{j+1})$ ;
14  else  $cut.remove(c_j)$ ;
15  return  $cut$ ;
```

1) *Lower bound using WLA*: The first idea is simply to use the exact algorithm for *WLA* by transforming a *single data* graph instance to a *multiple data* graph instance.

Let $G = (s, c_1, \dots, c_k)$ be a k -chain of root s and of chains c_1, \dots, c_k . We want to construct a graph G' such that:

- For any schedule ϕ , ϕ valid for $G \Leftrightarrow \phi$ valid for G' .
- For any schedule ϕ , $WSC_G(\phi) \geq WLA_{G'}(\phi)$.

This way, we can solve optimally *WLA* on G' , and use this cost as a lower bound for *WSC* on G .

In order to construct G' , we just need to define weights on each outgoing edge of s . Let w_s the weight of the outgoing edges from s in the initial graph G . The following lemma guides us in defining weights for G' :

Lemma 10. *Consider G' a copy of G , where the weight of the edge from s to c_i is w_i , for $1 \leq i \leq k$, and $\sum_{i=1}^k w_i = w_s$. Then, for any schedule ϕ , $WSC_G(\phi) \geq WLA_{G'}(\phi)$.*

Proof sketch. Only the cost of the very first edges changes, and we find the desired result with a simple computation that is described in Appendix A9. \square

Thus, we can transform any graph G in the single data model, by splitting the single data w_s into multiple data w_i 's to create a graph in the multiple data model, while ensuring that $\sum_{i=1}^k w_i = w_s$. Any distribution of the w_i 's could be considered, and we use $w_i = w_s/k$. We can then solve the problem for *WLA*, which gives us a lower bound for *WSC*.

2) *Lower bound using Linear Programming*: Another idea to get a lower bound on the cost of the optimal schedule for *WSC* is to formulate the problem as a set of linear constraints with integer variables, hence we can use an ILP solver to obtain the optimal solution or a bound on the solution. Note that this method applies to any graph, not only to k -chains.

Variables:

- $\forall i \in [1, n], t_i \in \mathbb{R}^+$: start of task i .
- $\forall (i, j) \in [1, n]^2, \text{PRED}_{i,j} \in \{0, 1\}$: whether i is taken before j in the schedule.
- $\text{LAST} \in \mathbb{R}^+$: start of the last neighbor of s .

Constraints:

- One task has to be first: $\forall i, j, \text{PRED}_{i,j} + \text{PRED}_{j,i} = 1$.
- The order is respected: $\forall (i, j) \in E, t_i \leq t_j$.
- If i is chosen before j , it should finish before j starts: $\forall i, j, t_i + c_i \leq t_j + \sum_k w_k \text{PRED}_{j,i}$.
- Last neighbor of s : $\forall i \in V^+(s), t_i \leq \text{LAST}$.

Objective function:

$$\min \sum_{i \in V \setminus \{s\}} \sum_{(j,k) \in E, j \neq s} \text{PRED}_{j,i} \text{PRED}_{i,k} w_{j,k} + w_s \text{LAST}.$$

In this formulation, there is a product of variables in the objective. But since these variables are binary, we can linearize them. To linearize $a \times b$, we replace it with a new binary variable c and add three constraints: $c \geq a + b - 1$, $c \leq a$, and $c \leq b$. These constraints indeed guarantee that $c = a \times b$.

From this set of constraints, we can use an ILP solver to search for the optimal solution, and it will also return some lower bounds from constructing the dual problem, even if provided with a limited time budget. The main issue is that the number of constraints grow quite fast, so it can sometimes be hard to even find one valid solution. One way to solve this issue is to feed our best known solution as initial solution to the solver. In the experiments, we use the best solution from LOCAL-SEARCH as a starting point and use a time budget. This gives us both a heuristic solution, called ILP, and a lower bound, denoted as LP lower bound.

VI. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In this section, we pursue two objectives: (i) we compare the performance of the exact and heuristic algorithms presented in the previous section for both *WSC* and *WLA* models on various type of graphs (k -chains, series-parallel graphs and general DAGs), and (ii) based on these algorithms, we study whether it is more interesting to focus on average memory or peak memory minimization when scheduling several task graphs in parallel on a shared memory system.

All the algorithms have been implemented in C++ and are available at [26]. We use the Boost Graph Library for fast and flexible implementation of graph structures, as well as Gurobi, a very fast parallel ILP solver. For the sake of comparison with peak memory minimization, we use the optimal algorithm proposed by Kayaaslan et al. [3] for SP-graphs.

We have used various tools to generate the task graphs on which we execute the heuristics. For k -chains, we randomly generated them, first by generating a root node and k starts of chains, then by adding the remaining nodes to randomly chosen chains, and finally by choosing the weights uniformly in a set interval (here, $[1, 100]$). Hence, we generated *small chains* of size 32, and *large chains* of size 128. Also, we used graphs generated by the TaGaDa library [27], which generates DAGs with different degrees of parallelism. We used a parallelism ratio of 60% and a size of 512 in the *large DAGs* experiments. Finally, we have also focused on *SP graphs*, also generated with TaGaDa, but using the `-fj` (fork join) option, which creates SP graphs.

A. Heuristic comparison

Before evaluating the performance of the heuristics in a parallel setting on general graphs, we start by comparing heuristics for the *WSC* problem on randomly generated chains. In Figure 10a, we plot the average memory usage normalized by OPT for the greedy algorithms, along with the RANDOM-CUT, ILP and LOCAL-SEARCH heuristics, as well as the two lower-bounds from Section V-D. Since the graphs are small, we can compute OPT with the exponential algorithm as described in Section IV-C.

The boxplots display the median and interquartile range (IQR) of the data, with whiskers extending to the highest and lowest non-outlier points. Outliers are shown as individual points beyond the whiskers. Here, each boxplot correspond to 50 different graphs.

As expected, the greedy algorithms perform poorly: GREEDY-MEM consistently generates schedule with an average memory consumption 30% higher than OPT. This is due to the fact that they lack knowledge of the graph's structure, leading to short term memory gains but significant long term disadvantages. In contrast, heuristics with full graph awareness perform significantly better: RANDOM-CUT is only 10% above OPT, and LOCAL-SEARCH almost always finds the optimal solution, failing by no more than 5%. Exploiting the cuts in the chains not only yields far better results than the greedy approaches, but it also proves to be a sufficiently powerful tool to achieve the optimal schedule search in most cases. Additionally, we observe that although ILP can find the optimal solution for small graphs, its lower bound is not always tight, even with a 180-second time limit. The lower bound obtained by reducing the problem to *WLA* is also not tight, as the transformation to *WLA* loses too much critical information about the graph.

In larger graphs, calculating OPT becomes infeasible due to its exponential complexity, and hence we compare the heuristics to the lower bounds. Figure 10b presents results similar to previously, but on larger k -chain graphs, and normalized by the best solution found by ILP. It is important to note that we still initialize the ILP with the best solution from LOCAL-SEARCH; however, it does not necessarily converge to the optimal solution. Therefore, we take its best result within a time limit of 180 seconds. Interestingly, the lower bound derived from the ILP is inferior to that obtained by reducing the problem to *WLA*. Nevertheless, we observe a significant gap of approximately 25% between the LOCAL-SEARCH solution and the lower bound.

These results suggest that the lower bounds, rather than the heuristics, are the primary concern, as indicated by our observations on smaller task graphs. This reinforces our initial intuition that leveraging graph cuts leads to high-quality solutions that outperform greedy algorithms and approach the optimal solution for k -chains. This intuition is further supported by Figure 10c, which illustrates the average memory usage of greedy heuristics for *WLA*, normalized by AVGGSPALGO. Once again, the greedy algorithms perform

Fig. 10: Comparison of various heuristics and bounds for WSC and WLA on different types of structures.

significantly worse, with GREEDY-MEM exhibiting an average memory usage that is 40% worse.

B. Comparison between PEAKSPALGO and AVGSPALGO

After assessing that the sophisticated heuristic performs well for WSC and WLA, we check whether the peak memory achieved by this heuristic is close to the optimal. Since there exists an $\mathcal{O}(n \log(n))$ exact algorithm for the peak in the *multiple data* memory model on SP graphs [3], we perform experiments for WLA on SP graphs. We denote the optimal algorithm for peak memory as PEAKSPALGO, and we still refer to the heuristic for WLA on SP graphs as AVGSPALGO.

Figure 11 shows two plots that compare PEAKSPALGO and AVGSPALGO for both the average memory (WLA) and peak memory problem on SP graphs. In Figure 11a, we observe that the schedule aimed at minimizing peak memory consumption almost never achieves the optimal solution for average memory. For larger graphs, it consistently performs about 5% worse. On a positive note, AVGSPALGO consistently outperforms PEAKSPALGO in terms of minimizing average memory. Most notably, as shown in Figure 11b, AVGSPALGO performs well in minimizing peak memory. It nearly always finds the optimal solution, with only rare instances where the solution is up to 20% worse. This indicates that, in addition to producing a schedule with better average memory, it still achieves a peak memory that remains relatively small.

C. Parallel execution

Finally, we compare the schedules produced by AVGSPALGO against the ones provided by PEAKSPALGO with task graphs executed in parallel. This corresponds to a setting where a common memory is shared by task graphs processed concurrently. The memory used is the sum of data used by each task graph at any given time.

In Figure 12, we plot, for different numbers of graphs in parallel, the cumulated peak memory when all task graphs are scheduled with AVGSPALGO, compared to when all task graphs are scheduled with PEAKSPALGO. As expected, using PEAKSPALGO results in consistently slightly smaller memory than AVGSPALGO for a single task graph. However, as soon as we consider a parallel setting, the overall peak starts being smaller for AVGSPALGO than for PEAKSPALGO. This happens in 75% of the cases for 16 task graphs, being on average 5% smaller. Our intuition seems validated: minimizing the peak of each individual task graph does not give good results for parallel processing as each task graph might reach its peak at a different time. Outside of these peaks, there is no control over the memory used, which explains why AVGSPALGO outperforms the state of the art method PEAKSPALGO that minimizes the peak memory.

VII. CONCLUSION

We investigated algorithms and heuristics for the WSC and WLA problem on various types of graphs. We expanded on the general knowledge of exact algorithms for the WSC algorithm on chains and pumpkins, and for WLA on pumpkins.

Experiments demonstrated that the proposed heuristics, particularly the local search perform well in practice, often finding solutions close to the optimal average memory. Additionally, they produce schedules with reasonably small peak memory. In parallel execution scenarios, the AVGSPALGO heuristic outperforms PEAKSPALGO, validating the hypothesis that minimizing average memory can lead to lower overall peak memory usage in parallel executions.

While this hypothesis has been experimentally verified, deriving theoretical guarantees on the obtained parallel peak is left open for future work.

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A. Additional proofs

1) Naive recursion is arbitrarily bad for WSC on r-2TSPG:

Lemma 11. Treating recursively each subgraph of an r-2TSPG graph can produce arbitrarily bad outputs for the WSC problem.

Proof. We consider schedules for the graph of Figure 13. On the one hand, $L_\phi = (s, a, b, c, d, t)$ is an optimal schedule for WSC if we treat both branches separately. The associated cost is $C(\phi) = 2 + T \times 2 + P + 1 + T(P + 1) + 2 \times P = TP + 3T + 3P + 3$. On the other hand, if we consider $L_{\phi'} = (s, a, c, b, d, t)$, a schedule that intertwines both subgraphs, its associated cost is: $C(\phi) = 2 + T \times 2 + T \times 2 + P + 1 + 2P = 3P + 4T + 3$.

Not only is ϕ not optimal, but we have $C(\phi) = \mathcal{O}(TP)$ while $C(\phi') = \mathcal{O}(\max(T, P))$. \square

In particular this means that the $\mathcal{O}(n^2)$ algorithm given in [21] for the SC version of r-2TSPG is not optimal anymore in the WSC problem.

2) Naive recursion is arbitrarily bad for WLA on chains:

Lemma 12. Treating each chains independantly on a k-chain graph can produce arbitrarily bad outputs for the WLA problem.

Proof. Consider two schedules for the graph in Figure 14: $L_\phi = (s, a, b, c, d)$, the optimal schedule if we treat both chains separately, and $L_{\phi'} = (s, a, c, b, d)$ the optimal schedule.

We have $C(\phi) = \mathcal{O}(TP)$ while $C(\phi') = \mathcal{O}(\min(T, P))$. \square

In particular, this means that the polynomial algorithm for optimal LA on out-trees [22] does not work out of the box for the weighted version.

3) Proof of Lemma 1:

Proof. We first prove that ϕ' is a schedule for G' :

Overlap: suppose we have an overlap, we have two nodes a_i, a_j with:

Fig. 13: r-2TSPG graph.

Fig. 14: 2-chain.

$$\begin{aligned} \phi'(a_j) &< \phi'(a_i) + t_i \\ \sum_{k=1}^{|V|} t_k - (\phi(a_j) + t_j) &< \sum_{k=1}^{|V|} t_k - (\phi(a_i) + t_i) + t_i \\ \phi(a_i) &< \phi(a_j) + t_j \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \phi'(a_i) &< \phi'(a_j) + t_j \\ \sum_{k=1}^{|V|} t_k - (\phi(a_i) + t_i) &< \sum_{k=1}^{|V|} t_k - (\phi(a_j) + t_j) + t_j \\ \phi(a_j) &< \phi(a_i) + t_i \end{aligned}$$

This contradicts that ϕ is a schedule for G as it has an overlap.

Finished: Suppose there is a node a_i that is not finished. We get:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi'(a_i) + t_i &> \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j \\ \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j - (\phi(a_i) + t_i) + t_i &> \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j \\ \phi(a_i) &< 0 \end{aligned}$$

This once again contradicts that ϕ is a valid schedule for G .

Dependencies: suppose the dependencies of G' are not respected. We have $(a_i, a_j) \in E'$ such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi'(a_i) &\geq \phi'(a_j) \\ \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j - (\phi(a_i) + t_i) &\geq \sum_{j=1}^{|V|} t_j - (\phi(a_j) + t_j) \\ \phi(a_j) + t_j &\geq \phi(a_i) + t_i \\ \phi(a_j) + t_j &> \phi(a_i) \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 15: Merge operation.

By construction of E' , we know that $(a_j, a_i) \in E$, and because ϕ is a valid schedule for G , we get $\phi(a_j) < \phi(a_i)$, and even $\phi(a_j) + t_j \leq \phi(a_i)$ (no overlap). This gives a direct contradiction.

Next, we prove that $WLA_G(\phi) = WLA_{G'}(\phi') + C$.

$$\begin{aligned}
WLA_{G'}(\phi') &= \sum_{(a_i, a_j) \in E'} w'_{a_i, a_j} (\phi'(a_j) - \phi'(a_i)) \\
&= \sum_{(a_i, a_j) \in E'} w'_{a_i, a_j} (\phi(a_i) + t_i - \phi(a_j) - t_j) \\
&= \sum_{(a_j, a_i) \in E} w_{a_j, a_i} (\phi(a_i) - \phi(a_j)) + \sum_{(a_j, a_i) \in E} w_{a_j, a_i} (t_i - t_j) \\
&= WLA_G(\phi) + C
\end{aligned}$$

This means that when ϕ is an optimal schedule for G , ϕ' is also an optimal schedule for G' . Indeed, suppose that there is a better schedule ψ' . We can consider its reverse schedule ψ for G .

We get $WLA_G(\psi) = WLA_{G'}(\psi') + C < WLA_{G'}(\phi') + C = WLA_G(\phi)$, which contradicts that ϕ is an optimal schedule for G . \square

4) *Proof of Lemma 5:* We first define some different edge types for a chain, and give a formal definition of the notion of graph compression.

Definition 13 (Rigid and elastic edge). *Let G be a DAG. An edge $(a_i, a_j) \in E$ is called rigid if, for any optimal schedule ϕ , we have $\phi(a_i) + t_i = \phi(a_j)$, i.e., a_j is scheduled immediately after a_i in any optimal schedule. If (a_i, a_j) is not rigid, we call it an elastic edge.*

Definition 14 (Merged nodes). *Let $G = (V, E)$, $(a_i, a_j) \in E$. We define the merge operation on nodes a_i and a_j by:*

- Add a node $a_{i,j}$ of weight $t_i + t_j$
- Replace each edge (a_j, a_k) by an edge $(a_{i,j}, a_k)$
- Replace each edge (a_k, a_i) by an edge $(a_k, a_{i,j})$
- Remove the nodes a_i and a_j

The resulting graph is denoted as $G_{(a_i, j)}$. We also define the merged schedule $\phi_{(a_i, j)}$. An example is given in Figure 15.

Lemma 13. *Let G be a chain, and $(a_i, a_j) \in E$ be a rigid edge. ϕ is an optimal schedule for WSC on G if and only if $\phi_{(a_i, j)}$ is an optimal schedule for WSC on $G_{(a_i, j)}$.*

Proof. Let us say that the successor of a_j is a_k . The main result of the proof is that:

$$WSC_G(\phi) = WSC_{G_{(a_i, j)}}(\phi_{(a_i, j)}) + t_i(w_{i,j} - w_{j,k})$$

$$\begin{aligned}
WSC_G(\phi) &= \sum_{u \in V} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v} (\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&= \sum_{u \in V \setminus \{a_i, a_j\} \cup \{a_{i,j}\}} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v} (\phi(v) - \phi(u) + w_{i,j} (\phi(a_j) - \phi(a_i)) \\
&\quad + w_{j,k} (\phi(a_k) - \phi(a_j)) - w_{j,k} (\phi_{(a_i, j)}(a_k) - \phi_{(a_i, j)}(a_{i,j}))
\end{aligned}$$

We now use the fact that (a_i, a_j) is rigid:

$$\begin{aligned}
WSC_G(\phi) &= WSC_{G_{(a_i, j)}}(\phi_{(a_i, j)}) + w_{i,j} t_i + w_{j,k} t_j - w_{j,k} (t_i + t_j) \\
&= WSC_{G_{(a_i, j)}}(\phi_{(a_i, j)}) + w_{i,j} (t_i - t_j)
\end{aligned}$$

Because (a_i, a_j) is rigid, we can always transform a schedule ϕ for G into $\phi_{(a_i, j)}$ for $G_{(a_i, j)}$. Because both costs are equal up to a constant, the optimality of ϕ means the optimality of $\phi_{(a_i, j)}$ and vice versa. \square

Lemma 14. *Let G be a k -chain tree. Let $a_i, a_j, a_k, a_l \in V$ be a part of one chain of G . If (a_j, a_k) is an elastic edge, then $R(a_j) \geq R(a_k)$.*

Proof. Because (a_j, a_k) is elastic, there exists an optimal ordering ϕ where a_k does not follow a_j immediately. We define the following quantities:

- S the set of nodes ordered between a_j and a_k in ϕ . We have $a \in S \Leftrightarrow \phi(v) < \phi(a) < \phi(w)$
- $E_L = \{(u, v) \in E \mid \phi(u) < \phi(a_j), v \in S, \phi(v) = \max_{v' \in V^+(u)} \phi(v')\}$ the edges from other branches that are in the cut when a_j is scheduled and finish in S .
- $E_R = \{(u, v) \in E \mid \phi(a_k) < \phi(v), u \in S, \phi(v) = \max_{v' \in V^+(u)} \phi(v')\}$ the edges from other branches that are in the cut when a_k is scheduled and start in S .
- $w_L = \sum_{(u,v) \in E_L} w_{u,v}$
- $w_R = \sum_{(u,v) \in E_R} w_{u,v}$

We consider two new schedules ϕ_j and ϕ_k that derive from ϕ . If $L_\phi = (\dots, a_j, S, a_k, \dots)$, then $L_{\phi_j} = (\dots, S, a_j, a_k, \dots)$ and $L_{\phi_k} = (\dots, a_j, a_k, S, \dots)$. Both are still valid schedules as a_j and a_k belong to another branch as the nodes of S .

Instead of computing the whole cost of each schedule, we can compute the difference between two schedules by looking at the variation in lengths of the different elastic edges involved. Figure 16 shows how these quantities evolve between each schedule. ϕ is supposed optimal, so we get:

$$\begin{aligned}
WSC_G(\phi_j) &\geq WSC_G(\phi) \\
w_R t_j + w_{i,j} \sum_{a \in S} t_a &\geq w_L t_j + w_{j,k} \sum_{a \in S} t_a \\
R(a_j) &= \frac{w_{i,j} - w_{j,k}}{t_j} \geq \frac{w_L - w_R}{\sum_{a \in S} t_a}
\end{aligned}$$

Fig. 16: Local swaps

We also have:

$$\begin{aligned}
WSC_G(\phi_k) &\geq WSC_G(\phi) \\
w_L t_k + w_{k,l} \sum_{a \in S} t_a &\geq w_R t_k + w_{j,k} \sum_{a \in S} t_a \\
\frac{w_L - w_R}{\sum_{a \in S} t_a} &\geq \frac{w_{j,k} - w_{k,l}}{t_k} = R(a_k)
\end{aligned}$$

We can then combine both inequations to get $R(a_j) \geq R(a_k)$, concluding the proof. \square

This first lemma gives a first way of compressing the graph: we know that for an edge to be elastic, the ratios along each chain have to be decreasing. If they are not, we can merge the nodes. There is a second criterion to merge more nodes together:

Definition 15 (Temp-min edge). *Let T be a k -chain tree. We consider one of its chain $C = (a_1, \dots, a_m)$. The edge (a_i, a_{i+1}) is a temporary minimal edge (abbreviated temp-min), if and only if $w_{i,i+1} = \min_{j \leq i} w_{j,j+1}$.*

In other words, it is a temporary minimal edge if its weight is the smallest on the chain yet. In particular, edges outgoing from the root are temp-mins.

Lemma 15. *Let T be a k -chain tree. If (a_i, a_j) is not a temp-min edge, then it is a rigid edge.*

This lemma states that the only edges that remain in the compressed graph are the temp-min ones, thus the weight of the edges along each chain will always be strictly decreasing. Once again, the proof follows the one from [11].

Proof. Let (u, v) be the a non temp-min edge in a chain C . Let u_1, \dots, u_n be the nodes of compressed chain C , i.e. with (u_i, u_{i+1}) all elastic edges. We suppose that (u, v) is elastic, so there is an i such that $(u_i, u_{i+1}) = (u, v)$. We choose (u, v) to be the first non temp-min edge that is elastic, so $(u_{i-1}, u_{i,i+1})$ is a temp-min. In particular, $w_{i-1,i} < w_{i,i+1}$.

We will add one edge of weight 0 in the end, together with a node u_{n+1} . This does not change the schedule nor its cost as we can always schedule u_{n+1} to be in last.

We have $R_G(u_i) = \frac{w_{i-1,i} - w_{i,i+1}}{w_i} < 0$. We know that the ratios are decreasing along the chain. We get $R_G(u_n) \leq R_G(u_{n-1}) \leq \dots \leq R_G(u_i) < 0$. Thus $\frac{w_{n-1,n} - w_{n,n+1}}{w_n} < 0$, and finally $w_{n-1,n} < 0$ because we set $w_{n,n+1}$ to 0. This contradicts that all the weights of our graph are positive.

We get a contradiction, so (u, v) has to be a rigid edge. \square

5) Proof of Lemma 6:

Proof. Let us consider an optimal schedule ϕ for WSC, with the chain $c = (a_1, \dots, a_i)$ ordered just before the chain $c' = (a'_1, \dots, a'_j)$ in the first phase of the schedule, with

$$\frac{t_i}{\sum_{l=1}^{k_i} w_{i,l}} > \frac{t_j}{\sum_{l=1}^{k_j} w_{j,l}}.$$

We know from the previous lemma that both chains are scheduled continuously.

We define ϕ' as the copy of ϕ , but with the chains c and c' swapped. ϕ and ϕ' are represented in Figure 17. We can see that the only edges modified are $w_{i,i+1}$ and $w'_{j,j+1}$. We get:

$$\begin{aligned}
C(\phi) &\leq C(\phi') \\
t_i \sum_{l=1}^{k_j} w_{j,l} &\leq t_j \sum_{l=1}^{k_i} w_{i,l}
\end{aligned}$$

This is a direct contradiction with our initial assumption, so all the chains need to be ordered by decreasing values of $\frac{t_i}{\sum_{j=1}^{k_i} w_{i,j}}$. \square

6) Proof of Lemma 9:

Proof. We prove that for a given schedule ϕ for G , $WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}) = C_{\phi_{[S]}} + WLA_{G'}(\phi_{[T]})$, with $C_{\phi_{[S]}}$ is a constant that only depends on $\phi_{[S]}$.

Fig. 17: Exchanging two chains in the first phase of a schedule

$$\begin{aligned}
WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}) &= \sum_{u \in V} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&= \sum_{u \in S} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&\quad + \sum_{u \in T} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&= \sum_{u \in S} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&\quad + \sum_{\substack{(u,v) \in E \\ u \in T}} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&= \sum_{u \in S} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&\quad + \sum_{\substack{(u,v) \in E' \\ u \neq s}} w_{u,v}(\phi_{[T]}(v) - \phi_{[T]}(u))
\end{aligned}$$

We can separate the first term whether u is next to the cut or not:

$$\begin{aligned}
\text{FIRST} &= \sum_{u \in S} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&= \sum_{\substack{u \in S \\ V^+(u) \cap T = \emptyset}} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&\quad + \sum_{\substack{(u,v) \in E \\ u \in S, v \in T}} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \\
&= \sum_{u \in S} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi_{[S]}(v) - \phi_{[S]}(u)) \\
&\quad + \sum_{\substack{(u,v) \in E \\ u \in S, v \in T}} w_{u,v}(\phi_{[T]}(v) - \phi_{[T]}(u)) \\
&= C_{\phi_{[S]}} + \sum_{\substack{(u,v) \in E' \\ u=s}} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u))
\end{aligned}$$

Which gives us:

$$\begin{aligned}
WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}) &= C_{\phi_{[S]}} + \sum_{(u,v) \in E'} w_{u,v}(\phi_{[T]}(v) - \phi_{[T]}(u)) \\
&= C_{\phi_{[S]}} + WLA_{G'}(\phi_{[T]})
\end{aligned}$$

Let us suppose that $\phi_{[S]} + \phi'$ is not optimal, i.e. $WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi') > WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]})$.

Thus we have $WLA_{G'}(\phi') = WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi') - C_{\phi_{[S]}} > WSC_G(\phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}) - C_{\phi_{[S]}} = WLA_{G'}(\phi_{[T]})$, which contradicts the fact that ϕ' is optimal for WLA on G' . \square

7) Proof of Lemma 3:

Proof. The main result is that for any schedule ϕ , $WLA_G(\phi) = WLA_{G'}(\phi) + \sum_{a_j \in V \setminus \{t\}} t_j$. This can be seen easily

if we look at the memory used by the chain c : wherever in the schedule up to the very end, exactly one edge of c is in the memory. If we diminish by 1 the value of the whole chain, then the total cost decreases by the length of c , which is always $\sum_{a_j \in V \setminus \{t\}} t_j$.

Let ϕ be an optimal schedule for WLA on G' . Because the dependencies of G' are the same as for G , ϕ is also a schedule for G . Suppose that there exists ψ a schedule for G such that $WLA_G(\psi) < WLA_G(\phi)$.

We then have:

$$WLA_{G'}(\psi) = WLA_G(\psi) - \sum_{a_j \in V \setminus \{t\}} t_j < WLA_G(\phi) - \sum_{a_j \in V \setminus \{t\}} t_j = WLA_{G'}(\phi)$$

This contradicts the optimality of ϕ for WLA on G' . \square

8) Proof of Lemma 4:

Proof. Let ϕ be an optimal schedule for WLA on G , with $L_\phi = (a_1, \dots, a_n)$. We can then define $\psi = \phi_{[S]} + \phi_{[T]}$. We will prove that ψ is a valid and optimal schedule for WLA on G .

Let us first prove that ψ is valid. Consider an edge $(a_i, a_j) \in E$. We want to prove that $\psi(a_i) < \psi(a_j)$. There are three cases:

- $a_i, a_j \in S$. Then $\phi_{[S]}(a_i) < \phi_{[S]}(a_j) \Rightarrow \psi(a_i) < \psi(a_j)$.
- $a_i, a_j \in T$. Then $\phi_{[T]}(a_i) < \phi_{[T]}(a_j) \Rightarrow \psi(a_i) < \psi(a_j)$.
- $a_i \in S, a_j \in T$. By construction, $\psi(a_i) < \psi(a_j)$.

We cannot have $a_i \in T, a_j \in S$ because (S, T) is a valid cut.

We will now prove that $WLA_G(\psi) \leq WLA_G(\phi)$. For this, we will consider the cost associated with a vertex $u \in V$ and a chain $c = (a_1, \dots, a_l)$ with $\phi(a_j) < \phi(u) < \phi(a_{j+1})$. The contribution for G is $t_u w_{j,j+1}$. Suppose that $a_i \in S$, once again, there are three cases:

- $a_j, a_{j+1} \in S$, we still have $\psi(a_j) < \psi(u) < \psi(a_{j+1})$, the contribution is still $t_u w_{j,j+1}$.
- $a_j \in S, a_{j+1} \in T$, then we still have $\psi(a_j) < \psi(u)$ because both are in S , and $\psi(u) < \psi(a_{j+1})$ because $u \in S, a_{j+1} \in T$. The contribution is still $t_u w_{j,j+1} = 0$.
- $a_j, a_{j+1} \in T$. Then, let k be the indice such that $a_k \in S, a_{k+1} \in T$, with $a_k, a_{k+1} \in c$. We now have $\psi(a_k) < \psi(a_j) < \psi(u)$ and $\psi(u) < \psi(a_{k+1})$. Thus the contribution is $t_u w_{k,k+1} = 0$.

In all three cases, the contribution of c for u is smaller or equal for ψ than for ϕ . If $u \in T$, we can do the same reasoning but in symmetry. Overall, we get $WLA_G(\psi) \leq WLA_G(\phi)$. \square

9) Proof of Lemma 10:

Proof. Let ϕ be a valid schedule for WSC on G .

$$WSC_G(\phi) \geq WLA_{G'}(\phi)$$

$$\sum_{u \in V} \max_{v \in V^+(u)} w_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u)) \geq \sum_{(u,v) \in E'} w'_{u,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(u))$$

because G and G' only differ at the start:

$$\begin{aligned} \max_{v \in V^+(s)} w_{s,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(s)) &\geq \sum_{v \in V^+(s)} w'_{s,v}(\phi(v) - \phi(s)) \\ w_s \max_{v \in V^+(s)} \phi(v) &\geq \sum_{v_i \in V^+(s)} w_i \phi(v_i) \\ \sum_{v_i \in V^+(s)} w_i \max_{v \in V^+(s)} \phi(v) &\geq \sum_{v_i \in V^+(s)} w_i \phi(v_i) \end{aligned}$$

\square

B. Algorithms

1) Greedy algorithm for WSC:

Algorithm 2: minSCGreedy(root, cmp)

Input : root of G , cmp comparison function for vertices
Output: Schedule obtained greedily

```

1 pq ← PriorityQueue(cmp);
2 pq.push(root);
3 s ← Schedule();
4 while pq is not empty do
5   u ← pq.pop();
6   if u is not in s then
7     s.append(u);
8     foreach v ∈ V+(u) do
9       pq.push(v);
10    end
11  end
12 end
13 return s;
```

2) Random cut algorithm for WSC:

Algorithm 3: minSCRANDOMCut(G, N)

Input : Graph G , of root $root$. N number of cuts drawn
Output: Best schedule found

```

1 bestSchedule ← None
2 for i = 1 to N do
3   cut ← RandomCut();
4   s ← ConstructSchedule( $G$ , cut);
5   if SCCost( $s, G$ ) < SCCost(bestSchedule,  $G$ ) then
6     bestSchedule = s;
7   end
8 end
9 return bestSchedule;
```
